

Fertilizer management

Response of rice hybrids to N sources and time of application of N and K

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Although $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ has been accepted as the preferred N source in rice, $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ was reported to be the preferred source in China at late crop growth stages when hybrid exhibited a peak demand for nutrients. A higher percentage of unfilled grains is common in hybrid rices unless the soil nutrient supply can cope with crop demands. Thus, delayed application of N and K coinciding with flowering can help realize the potential of hybrid rices.

We studied the differential response of recently released hybrids to various N sources and split application of N

and K. In a Vertisol (typical Pellustert), during the 1994 and 1996 wet season, four hybrids (MGR1, KRH1, APRH1, and APRH2) received the following N treatments: 120 kg ha⁻¹ at 33:33:33% at the basal, tillering, and flowering stages, respectively; and 120 kg ha⁻¹ likewise at the basal, tillering, plant initiation, and flowering stages. All phosphorus was applied basally (P at 26.4 kg ha⁻¹). Potash was either applied as basal or in two splits (75% basal and 25% at flowering). Data on grain and straw yields and their N uptake were recorded.

Of the two N sources tested, $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ was found to be superior for grain yield (5.3 t ha⁻¹) and N uptake (128 kg ha⁻¹). This indicated that the more stable $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ held by the soil cation exchange complex (CEC) affected yield. Although the usefulness of $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ for hybrids at the reproductive stage has

been reported, it leached and was unstable. Three equal N split applications were on a par with four N splits. Irrespective of N sources, a topdressing of N beyond the panicle initiation stage for short- and mid-duration groups did not bestow any additional yield advantage. Similarly, a split application of K (twice) did not affect either grain yield or N uptake even though an adequate K supply at flowering was known to improve grain filling via the efficient translocation of photosynthates to the sink. High levels of available K present at the experimental site might have taken care of the crop needs.

The present study indicated that $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ is a better source of N for hybrids. In Vertisols with a high CEC contributing to the retention of applied $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ and high available K status, there is no need to resort to delayed N and K application. ■

Nitrogen response of Karnataka Rice Hybrid 2

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The development of hybrids, because of their heterotic vigor, could increase rice productivity by breaking the yield barrier. With this objective, two rice hybrids—Karnataka Rice Hybrid 1 (KRH1) and Karnataka Rice Hybrid 2 (KRH2)—were released in Karnataka. Hybrids in most crops usually require an increased use of various nutrients, especially N.

To determine the N requirement in KRH2, a medium-duration rice hybrid, a study was undertaken using IR20 as a check variety. Experiments were laid out with different levels of N, ranging from 0 to 200 kg ha⁻¹, on a sandy loam soil with a pH of 6.5 and organic C of 0.5% in a split-plot design with three replications during the 1994-96 wet seasons.

KRH2 outyielded IR20 at all levels of N application, ranging from 0 to 200 kg ha⁻¹. In IR20, the tiller number was higher than that of KRH2. The increased yield of KRH2 was mainly attributed to the higher number of productive tillers, panicle weight, and number of filled grains. The nutrients

used for the production of unproductive tillers in IR20 might have been better used in KRH2 to increase seed set, panicle weight, and thus yield. IR20 responded to applied N only up to 100 kg ha⁻¹. In KRH2, the response to applied N beyond 100 kg ha⁻¹ was marginal and insignificant. ■

Integrated pest management — diseases

The effect of *Trichoderma* and antifungal agents on rice germination

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Rice seeds were found to exhibit very weak or no germination when sown in an antifungal seed-raising mix made by cultivating the forest green mold, *Trichoderma viride*, in nutrient-supplemented sawdust from *Pinus radiata* wood. (*P. radiata* is a common temperate plantation softwood that is grown extensively in southern

hemisphere countries for lumber.) *Trichoderma* is a genus of pathogenic fungi used widely in horticulture against such fungal diseases as silver-leaf in fruit trees. The aim of the antifungal mix is to provide a natural control agent against damping down or seedling wilt diseases using a cheap and abundant plant waste.

Common vegetables (carrot, radish, lettuce, tomato) germinated and grew extremely well in the antifungal mix with no disease mortality. But when four rice varieties (IR60 HD 105, PSBRe4 HD 437, PSBRe2 HD 429, and PSBRc10 HD 439) were tried in the new

mix, the germination percentage ranged from 0 to 2%. Growth of those seeds that did germinate was extremely poor.

This unexpected result could be explained by *T. viride* being toxic to rice but not to the other plants tested. The mechanisms for this toxicity could be either exosomatic, through the rice being especially sensitive to *T. viride* toxins released in the rhizosphere, or endosomatic, through the habit of rice of phagocytizing soil organic materials in heterophagous nutrition—toxins of *T. viride* origin might be brought into the rice root to make intimate connection with the rice cytoplasm. Thus, *T. viride* would especially affect rice but not other plants that lack the phagocytic habit.

An alternative hypothesis is that rice might have a specific requirement for a mycorrhizal symbiont that is killed by the *T. viride*, hence the poor or zero germination.

In an attempt to test these hypotheses, trials were conducted in which 100 seed lots of rice were germinated on damp filter paper after being treated with dilute solutions of antifungicides. Copper oxychloride, benlate, and hydrogen peroxide were used in weak

Germination and growth of lots of 100 seeds of rice variety PSBRc4 HD 437 on filter paper subjected to antifungal treatments.

Factor	Treatment				
	None	1% hydrogen peroxide	1% copper oxychloride	1% benomyl benlate	0.01% <i>Spirulina platensis</i>
Germination (%)	98	98	98	100	100
Total wet weight (g) at 20 d postplanting	5.627	6.305	6.496	5.652	7.730
Maximum stem height (mm) at 19 d postplanting	50	60	57	53	59
Max. root length (mm) at 6 d	20	25	35	22	30

concentrations that did not affect the germination of other plant species (barley, oat, and wheat). One hundred seed lots were also germinated in the presence of a small amount of *Spirulina platensis*, a commonly available cyanobacterium. The experiments were repeated with dehulled rice seeds. Three replicates of all trials were conducted.

Compared with the controls, all the antifungicides stimulated growth. Germination and growth were enhanced over the controls when rice was germinated in the presence of *S. platensis* (see table).

These results suggest that microorganisms can affect the early growth of rice. In practical management, fungi-

cides can improve germination. Seed-raising mixes contaminated with *Trichoderma* spp. or other fungi that are inhibitors to growth should be avoided.

Another interesting result from this work is that germination and growth might be enhanced if a small quantity of *S. platensis* is added to the seeds at planting time. *S. platensis* is a N₂-fixing photoautotroph that grows actively in damp conditions, thus possibly increasing the N available to the seedlings as well as providing an additional carbon source. It also contains powerful antifungal and antiviral compounds that could protect the seed and emerging seedling from attack by microorganisms. ■

Integrated pest management — insects

Evolving insecticide use and practices at IIRI

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With growing awareness of the concerns associated with pesticide (especially insecticide) use, IIRI has acted over the past decade to play a lead role in both reducing insecticide use and promoting safe pesticide use for people and the environment. In addition to the direct steps taken at the IIRI experiment station, a book has also been produced by IIRI (in 1995) addressing areas of concern related to pesticides, farmer health, and the rice environment. The improvements made at the IIRI experiment station include

1. Implementation of a trained pesticide applicators (TPA) program (1987).
2. A ban on World Health Organization (WHO) Category One pesticides (1989).
3. Implementation of a regular scheme to monitor insect, disease, and weed populations in fields (1991).
4. Endorsement of integrated pest management (IPM) as the standard for pest management at the IIRI station (1995).
5. Further changes in application methods and monitoring of fields (1997).

We detail each of these steps below.

1. Trained Pesticide Applicators program (1987)

To improve the safe use of pesticides, IIRI introduced a system of “authorized pesticide applications” in 1987. (The name was subsequently changed to trained pesticide applicators, TPA.) The system includes guidelines for (1) certification process (training), (2) routine medical examinations and health reporting, (3) use of personal protective equipment, (4) job rotation, (5) decontamination facilities, and (6) safe product disposal.

This system ensures that pesticide applications are made by trained staff, resulting in improved application with benefits to both users and the environment.